

Design of an experimental setup to measure friction with a comparison for UD C/PAEK tapes in melt

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Abstract

In the manufacture of laminated composites, the friction between adjacent plies or with the tooling surface, in combination with other deformation mechanisms, can lead to defects. Proper friction experiments are, therefore, essential to understand the material behavior during processing, as well as to develop more advanced friction models for process simulations to predict the manufacturing result beforehand. In this work, we present the design of a new experimental setup, based on our original friction tester, to perform friction experiments with accurate control over the sliding rate, normal pressure, and temperature. The pressure platens can be opened to ease specimen mounting and alignment, while more advanced experiments, e.g. varying-rate friction, are now possible. We measured the ply-ply friction of UD C/PEEK and C/LM-PAEK in melt for a range of sliding rates with both the new and original setup, yielding comparable results. This new setup enables more advanced friction testing in future work.

Keywords: Experimental setup; Design; Thermoplastic matrix composites (TPCs); Ply-ply friction.

1 Introduction

Processing defects, such as wrinkles or ply splits, can occur during the manufacture of composite parts [1–3]. These defects can deteriorate the part performance once in service and, therefore, need to be avoided [4, 5]. Among other deformation mechanisms, the friction between adjacent plies as well as the friction between the surface plies and tooling plays a key role on the formation of defects during composite manufacturing [1, 2, 6]. Hence, a proper understanding of the friction behavior by means of characterization experiments is helpful for the manufacturing process. The friction results from these characterization experiments can also be used as an input for process simulation software [6, 7], facilitating the design stage to enable first-time-right defect-free manufacturing.

Of course, the friction characterization experiments need to simulate the conditions during manufacturing in the best way possible to yield accurate results, which can be quite challenging. In particular for thermoplastic matrix composites (TPCs) used in aircraft, the type of material considered in this work. These aerospace grade TPCs are typically processed at a significantly higher temperature compared to their more conventional thermoset counterparts [8, 9].

Some of the first studies on the friction characterization for TPCs either pulled material from a stack of plies [10] or used a friction sled [11]. The former approach found most follow-up in subsequent designs of experimental setups by several research groups [12–19]. Hence, several purpose-built setups exist to measure the friction for different materials under various conditions. Earlier, a benchmark on the friction between TPC plies and tooling, i.e. tool-ply friction, was initiated to compare different setups, resulting in several design recommendations [18]. These recommendations will be summarized in Section 2, as they formed an important input for the design process in this work.

The friction tester developed at the University of Twente more than a decade ago [20, 21] was also part of this friction benchmark. This original friction tester was used in several studies over the past years to measure the friction of various materials under different conditions [1, 22–29], ranging from dry carbon fiber weaves at sliding rates of 0.03 and 1000 mm/min to UD C/PEEK at a temperature of 420 °C and under a normal pressure of 220 kPa. We used the same setup in our recent work [30–33] to investigate the ply-ply friction for UD C/PAEK tapes in melt, resulting in a transient friction model that describes the measured response for different constant sliding rates. Hence, the original setup facilitated several studies on friction under different conditions, though we have reached the limits of the original

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friction tester. We would like to explore, for instance, the ply-ply friction response for different fiber orientations, force control, and arbitrary sliding-rate profiles, while these types of measurements are currently not possible.

This work presents the design of a new friction tester, in particular aimed to measure the friction for aerospace grade TPCs under conditions representative to their manufacturing. The design is based on the proven principles of our original and other setups, the recommendations from the benchmark exercise on tool-ply friction [18], and our advancing insights. We will compare the new friction tester with our original setup by means of flow curves, showing the measured peak and long-time friction for a range of applied sliding rates.

2 New friction tester design

The wish to broaden the possibilities of friction characterization for TPCs stimulated the development of a new friction tester at the University of Twente, succeeding the original friction tester (oFT) [20, 21, 34]. Other issues related to the user-friendliness, the control over the applied sliding rate, normal pressure, and temperature as well as the data acquisition further motivated a new setup. The recommendations from the tool-ply friction benchmark exercise [18] will be revisited first, followed by the proven principles of our original and other setups in literature. These lessons learned combined with our advancing insights formed the starting point for the design of the new friction tester, which is presented at the end of this section.

2.1 Friction benchmark and lessons learned

More than a decade ago, a benchmark on tool-ply friction was performed to compare friction testers from different institutes [18]. Two series of friction tests were performed between mild steel and commingled glass/PP fabric (commercially known as Twintex PP): one at room temperature and a second series of tests at temperatures above the melting point of polypropylene.

In the first series at room temperature, the friction results of each setup were reasonably precise, according to the reported average coefficient of variation of less than 5%. However, when comparing the friction responses as measured with the setups for different sliding rates and normal pressures, consistently lower or higher friction values than the average response were observed depending on the setup. This systematic deviation in the measured friction questions the accuracy of the obtained results and several recommendations were proposed.

The second series of friction tests at an elevated temperature were only conducted with three setups for a limited number of test conditions, making it harder to draw conclusions. However, the obtained friction curves (e.g. the stress growth at start-up, appearance of a stationary response, measurement noise, and standard deviation) as well

as the dependency of the measured friction on the test variables led to more design recommendations.

Most recommendations concern the pressure distribution, of which the uniformity needs to be checked. The importance of a proper pressure distribution in friction testing was already stressed by Ten Thije and Akkerman [34]. Regarding the structural design, deflections and misalignment of the pressure platens need to be avoided, as these negatively influence the pressure distribution. The applied normal force should be exerted in the center of the contact area and care should be taken to support the pressure platens close to the contact area. Furthermore, the reaction forces due to sliding of the specimen can cause tilting of the pressure platens, which needs to be avoided. It was, therefore, advised to clamp the stationary part of the specimen to the supporting frame instead of solely on the pressure platens to properly support the reaction forces. The setups involved in the benchmark were based on either a pull-through configuration, where the contact area remains constant during a test as new material enters between the pressure platens while sliding, or a pull-out configuration, where the contact area reduces as part of the specimen is pulled out. The former was favored as the applied pressure remains constant during a sliding experiment with such a configuration.

A pull-through test, however, requires a more advanced heating solution to ensure that the pulled-in material is adequately heated, another recommendation of the benchmark [18]. A climate chamber can be used to heat the whole setup and specimen, though the sensors then need to be positioned at a safe distance from the specimen to protect them from the heat, consequently reducing the measurement accuracy. Local heating of the material by means of the pressure platens allows a more direct measurement of the forces

Fig. 1: Schematic illustration of the new friction tester with a ply-ply friction test specimen clamped between two heated pressure platens. The air bellow actuates the lower platen, where the normal force F_n is actively controlled using the force measured with three compression load cells. The central UD tape is pulled out on the right at a sliding rate V with a pull force F_{pull} , while new material enters the contact area at the left, i.e. a pull-through configuration.

and displacement, as the sensors can be placed closer to the specimen. The required heating time and, with that, the measurement time, is also lower with local heating. A final recommendation of the benchmark relates to edge effects that can play a role in a pull-through test, for which a large contact area and chamfering of the pressure platens' edges were advised.

Several design solutions for our new friction tester are based on our experience with our original friction tester (oFT) [20,21,34]. A pull-through configuration, as used with the original setup, is pursued for the new friction tester as well to obtain a proper pressure distribution. The proven principle of using an air bellow with a moveable pressure platen instead of a linear guiding system is also used for the new design, as it allows settlement of the moveable pressure platen against the fixed pressure platen. This settlement of the platens theoretically yields a more homogeneous pressure distribution. However, the guiding system as well as the supporting structure as used in the oFT requires a major redesign to, among others, reduce the slack in device, allow for friction tests with different fiber orientations, and improve the overall user-friendliness.

Other limitations of the oFT concern the application of the applied normal pressure. First, the applied normal pressure should be actively controlled instead of manually. Secondly, the configuration of the load cells used to measure the normal forces should be redesigned, as the readings are currently affected by the internal stiffness of the device through adjustment springs that run in parallel (see Fig. 3 in the paper of Sachs et al. [25]). These adjustment springs are required to improve the alignment of the pressure platens, which is complicated by the vertical configuration of the platens due to the act of gravity. Shifting to a horizontal test configuration alleviates the issues related to gravity. Further, the normal force distribution can be measured more accurately by means of multiple compression load cells

placed in a triangle close to one of the pressure platens, as was done by e.g. Fetfatsidis et al. [15].

The procedure to insert a specimen in the oFT needs to be improved by means of a better accessibility, for which the setup of KU Leuven [35] with one of the pressure platens hinged on one side serves as an inspiration. Further, the control over the sliding movement can be improved, with the aim to perform varying-rate and force-controlled experiments. A stand-alone setup is pursued to reduce slack and stiffness issues, while providing an overall good alignment of the pressure platens, the specimen, and the pulling direction for prolonged use.

2.2 New friction tester design

A schematic illustration of the new friction tester is presented in Fig. 1, showing the general concept for a ply-ply friction experiment with UD tapes. In short, two heated pressure platens depicted in dark gray clamp a ply-ply friction test specimen. The upper pressure platen is fixed, while the lower pressure platen is actuated by an air bellow. Compression load cells are placed between the lower pressure platen and the air bellow. The specimen consists of a central UD tape, fixed at the right, and two outer plies, fixed at the left. The specimen is sandwiched between metal foils to protect the pressure platens from the molten matrix material. During an experiment, the central ply is pulled at a pull force F_{pull} to slide against the outer plies with a sliding rate V . New material of the central ply enters at the left during sliding, keeping the contact area of the three plies between the pressure platens constant, i.e. a pull-through configuration. In case of a tool-ply friction experiment, the two outer tapes surrounding the central ply are absent and, therefore, the central ply slides against the metal foils, mimicking the tooling surface.

Fig. 2: Overview pictures of the new friction tester with (a) closed and (b) opened upper plate on which the upper pressure platen is mounted. The open position eases specimen mounting. When closed, the pressure platens face each other and the pull clamp can be moved towards the left to clamp the central ply (see Fig. 1), after which a friction experiment can be performed.

Fig. 3: Detailed pictures of the new friction tester in open position with: (a) the pressure platens of $100 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$, labeled with II (lower) and III (upper, underneath a mounted specimen), where the notches on each corner (I) minimize the slack between the upper plate and the supporting frame in closed position; (b) the guiding system, which controls the movement of the lower pressure platen. The blue and green lines denote the rotational and translational degrees of freedom, respectively.

Fig. 4: Schematic cross-section of a part of the new friction tester design in length direction, illustrating the guiding system, which controls the vertical translation of the lower pressure platen (z -direction) with a linear guide, while providing rotational degrees of freedom (DoFs) in the x, y -plane. The air bellow actuates the lower platen, while the counterweight balances the guiding system.

The whole stand-alone setup, as shown in Fig. 2a, measures slightly larger than 2 m with from left-to-right a frame for the guiding system and its counterweight, an assembly with the pressure platens, an area where the pull clamp acts, a casing containing the data acquisition (DAQ) and control systems with a touchscreen attached in front, and the servo motor at the very right, which actuates the pull clamp.

The upper plate, indicated in Fig. 2a, is hinged on the right to the supporting frame. This hinge enables opening the pressure platens, as shown in Fig. 2b and in more detail in Fig. 3a. The open position eases specimen mounting di-

rectly on the upper plate using a line clamp, where laser lines alongside the upper pressure platen assist in the alignment of a specimen. A specimen mounted on the upper plate is shown in Fig. 3a, labeled with III.

The upper and lower pressure platens face each other when the upper plate is in closed position. The upper plate then rests on four notches, of which one is labeled with I in Fig. 3a. These notches minimize the slack between the upper plate and supporting frame, while four clamps fasten these two components. The contact area between the pressure platens of the new friction tester doubled in size compared with the oFT from $50 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$ to 100 mm long and 50 mm wide. This larger contact area is chosen to reduce the edge effects [18].

A guiding system controls the vertical translation of the lower pressure platen, of which a close-up and a schematic illustration are shown in Fig. 3b and 4, respectively. The lower pressure platen is mounted on a base plate, which is connected to the guiding system. This guiding system allows for vertical translation and rotation over the in-plane axes of the lower pressure platen, as indicated in Fig. 3b by the green arrow and blue lines, respectively, while fixing the other degrees of freedom. The components for the translational and rotational degrees of freedom are also indicated in the schematic illustration in Fig. 4. The additional rotational freedom allows settlement of the pressure platens for a proper pressure distribution. The weight of the guiding system is balanced by a counterweight, as shown on the very left in Fig. 2a and 4. The base plate on which the lower pressure platen is mounted is also separately balanced using small counterweights on the corners. The homogeneity of the pressure distribution between the platens at rest was qualitatively verified using pressure-sensitive film (Fujifilm Prescale 4LW [36]), which can be used at room temperature.

Fig. 5: Qualitative pressure distribution between the platens of the nFT under a normal pressure of 100 kPa at room temperature using Fuji Prescale 4LW pressure-sensitive film [36].

Fig. 6: Detailed picture of the air bellow (labeled with VI in the picture) beneath the lower pressure platen (IV), which actuates the vertical movement of the lower platen to apply a certain normal pressure. Three load cells (V) between the pressure platen and the air bellow are used to actively control the total normal force through the air pressure in the bellow as well as to check the normal force distribution.

This pressure-sensitive film colors pink when subjected to pressure, where the color intensity is a qualitative measure for the pressure magnitude. One of the colored pressure films is shown in Fig. 5. The homogeneous color over the contact area indicates a proper pressure distribution be-

tween the pressure platens in the nFT at room temperature and at rest.

The base plate below the lower pressure platen is actuated by a Norgren PM/31023 air bellow [37], as labeled with VI in the detailed picture in Fig. 6. Three HBM C2 compression load cells of 500 N each [38], labeled with V in Fig. 6, are located between the base plate and the lower pressure platen. These load cells are placed on a circle with 120° spacing to measure the normal force distribution and, with that, the total normal force. This total normal force is used to actively control the applied pressure in the air bellow using Bürkert 2871 solenoid control valves [39] operated via LabVIEW [40], resulting in an accuracy of ± 0.1 N on the total normal force. The system is capable of reaching a total normal force of 600 N on top of the weight of the lower pressure platen assembly.

An elevated temperature is provided by six heating cartridges per pressure platen (1000 W). A pre-heating stage of 30 mm long, a slightly deepened part on the pressure platens, heats up the additional material that enters the contact area during a test (see the schematic illustration in Fig. 1). The edge between the contact area and the pre-heating stage is chamfered to reduce the edge effects [18]. A thermocouple in each platen is used to actively control the temperature with Eurotherm 3216 PID controllers [41]. The setup is capable of reaching a test temperature of up to 450 °C.

The temperature distribution over the pressure platens was measured using ten thermocouples sandwiched between metal foils at a setpoint temperature of 385 °C. The deviation in the measured temperatures with respect to the setpoint at the ten locations is schematically illustrated in Fig. 7. The difference between the average temperature in the contact area and the setpoint was found to be 2.5 °C, with a maximum of 5.4 °C. The temperature in the pre-heating stage, at 15 mm from the edge of the contact area, was slightly lower, on average 3.5 °C.

The frame of the friction tester is designed to handle a maximum pull force of 10 kN. Two steel bars parallel to the sliding action at either side of the setup provide the required stiffness to the supporting frame, as seen in the overview picture in Fig. 2a. The setup compliance was found to be sufficiently low not to affect the friction measurements, with only a small clamp-to-clamp displacement in the order of 0.01 mm when subjecting a stiff bar to the typical pull force as observed during friction measurements. Similarly, the slack in the setup was also around 0.01 mm, which was checked by measuring the displacements of different components at several positions during friction tests (e.g. the upper plate as denoted in Fig. 2a).

A linear servo system from Festo [42] actuates the pull clamp between the stiffness bars in horizontal direction (see Fig. 2a), which is able to apply a maximum rate of 30 mm/s and is controlled via the accompanied Festo Automation Suite. This software enables one to prescribe arbitrary displacement profiles. A laser distance sensor (Baumer OM70-PO250.HH0240.VI [43]) mounted on the pull clamp mea-

Table 1: Characteristics of the new friction tester.

Variable	Unit	Value	Comment
Max. temperature	[°C]	450	Maximum attainable test temperature
Heating time	[min]	10	Time required to heat to 385 °C
Temperature accuracy	[°C]	≈ 2.5	Accuracy of temperature in contact area with respect to a setpoint of 385 °C
Temp. distribution	[°C]	≈ 5.5	Max. deviation in temperature over contact area with a setpoint temperature of 385 °C
Preheating temp.	[°C]	≈ -3.5	Deviation in temperature in preheating stage at 15 mm from the contact area at 385 °C
Normal force meas.	[-]	-	Three load cells positioned below the lower pressure platen on a circle with 120° spacing
Normal force precision	[N]	≈ 1	Precision of normal force measurement
Normal force accuracy	[N]	≈ 0.6	Accuracy of total measured normal force
Pressure range	[kPa]	2-150	Attainable normal pressure range
Pressure precision	[kPa]	≈ 0.1	Precision of normal pressure controller
Contact area size	[mm ²]	100 × 50	Contact area length times width
Setup compliance	[mm]	≈ 0.01	Clamp-to-clamp displacement for 500 N
Slack in setup	[mm]	≈ 0.01	Meas. at different locations during friction test
Max sliding rate	[mm/s]	30	Maximum attainable sliding rate
Test configurations	[°]	0 & 90°	Possible fiber orientations that can be clamped
Sampling rate	[Hz]	100	Sampling rate of data logging

Fig. 7: Deviation in temperature with respect to a setpoint temperature of 385 °C (black values in °C), measured with ten thermocouples between the pressure platens on the indicated positions. Two temperatures at the top of the schematic indicate the temperature measured in the pre-heating stage, while the other eight temperatures were measured in the contact area. Dimensions illustrated in gray in mm.

measures the distance to the upper pressure platen, as indicated in Fig. 2a. A 5 kN load cell with lateral force correction (HBM U10M [38]) measures the pull force and the data is logged at 100 Hz using LabVIEW [40], which is running on the touchscreen (see Fig. 2). Besides data logging, the LabVIEW program is also used as the main program to conduct a friction experiment, e.g. setting the normal pressure setpoint, moving the actuator, and saving the measured data.

The key characteristics of the new friction tester are listed in Table 1, which concludes this section on the design of the new setup. In the remainder of this work, we will compare the ply-ply friction as measured with the original and new friction tester, for which the materials and methods used for the ply-ply friction experiments will be presented next.

3 Materials and methods

3.1 Materials

Two thermoplastic composite tapes from Toray Advanced Composites [44], C/PEEK (TC1200) and C/LM-PAEK (TC1225), were investigated in this work. Both materials are reinforced with aligned (UD) continuous carbon fibers with a volume fraction of around 59%. The former has a Victrex PEEK 150P matrix, while the latter is pre-impregnated with Victrex LM-PAEK AE250 [45]. According to the manufacturer, the advised processing temperature ranges between 370-400 °C and 340-385 °C for C/PEEK and C/LM-PAEK, with the lower limits around 30 °C above the respective melting points.

3.2 Ply-ply friction experiment

The materials were both tested on the original (oFT) and the new friction tester (nFT). The latter was introduced in detail in Section 2, while the reader is kindly referred to references [20,21] for more information on the oFT. Specimens for the oFT and nFT were cut from the same roll, for both materials, to avoid batch-to-batch differences. The dimensions of the outer plies were $120 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$ for the oFT and $162 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$ for the nFT. The central plies were 250 mm and 208 mm long, for the oFT and nFT, respectively, and again both 50 mm wide. All fibers were aligned with the longitudinal direction, which corresponds to the sliding direction. The outer and central plies overlapped for a length of 65 mm and 115 mm for the oFT and nFT, respectively, leading to an additional overlap of 15 mm on top of the pressure platen's length in both setups to provide a pull-through test, as schematically illustrated in Fig. 1. The three plies were held together using paperclips (oFT) and by means of spot welds (nFT) to ease specimen mounting. A laser line leveler was used for alignment of the specimen in the oFT, while the projected laser lines assisted the proper mounting in the nFT. In both setups, metal foils were used to protect the pressure platens from contact with the molten matrix material.

The procedure and main result of a ply-ply friction experiment are schematically illustrated in Fig. 8. First, a dwell time t_{dwell} is used to melt the thermoplastic matrix in the specimen, after which a constant sliding rate V is applied, as shown in the top graph. A pull force F_{pull} is required to slide the central ply against the outer plies, from which the shear stress response per slip interface can be computed as follows:

$$\tau = \frac{F_{\text{pull}}}{2A}, \quad (1)$$

with A the contact area of $50 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$ for the oFT and $100 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$ for the nFT. The resulting shear stress response is illustrated in the bottom graph in Fig 8. The typical friction response exhibits a peak shear stress τ_p followed by a decrease in shear stress towards a steady-state or long-time shear stress τ_∞ . The shear stress relaxes to a residual or yield stress τ_y once the sliding action ceased, as observed in our earlier experimental work [30, 31] and schematically illustrated in Fig. 8. This yield stress is possibly caused by the interactions between fibers of the adjacent plies [46–48] and, therefore, can be subtracted from the measured shear stress to obtain the matrix shear stress:

$$\tau_{\text{mat}} = \tau - \tau_y. \quad (2)$$

Computation of the matrix shear stress eases the comparison of the friction data measured in this work with our earlier work, in which we found a correlation between the measured matrix shear stress and the modeled viscoelastic response of the matrix material at the ply-ply interface [31–33].

Fig. 8: Schematic illustration of a ply-ply friction experiment, showing the applied sliding rate V (top graph) and the resulting shear stress response τ (bottom graph) with a peak τ_p followed by a steady-state or long-time shear stress τ_∞ . After cessation of the sliding action, the stress relaxes towards a residual stress, interpreted as a yield stress τ_y , from which the matrix shear stress τ_{mat} can be computed according to Eq. (2). Illustration adapted from [31].

3.3 Test conditions

Ply-ply friction experiments were conducted with the aim to compare the oFT and the nFT. Experiments were performed for different constant sliding rates ranging from 1 to 200 mm/min for both C/PEEK and C/LM-PAEK tapes. Measurements at a sliding rate of 1, 5, 25, and 125 mm/min were performed in triplicate. Additionally, other sliding rates were measured to complete the flow curve of shear stress versus the applied sliding rate. At least 20 tests were performed per material and setup, with each experiment using a new specimen.

All experiments were carried out at a constant temperature, 385 °C and 365 °C for C/PEEK and C/LM-PAEK, respectively, and under a constant normal pressure of 15 kPa. A dwell time t_{dwell} of 5 minutes was used, starting from the moment at which the normal pressure was applied. The friction response was measured for a ply-ply sliding displacement of 10 mm, followed by one minute of stress relaxation. The pull force, normal forces, time, and displacement were logged with a sampling rate of at least 100 Hz.

4 Results and discussion

The new friction tester (nFT) as designed and built in this study works well and eases the characterization of the ply-ply friction for TPC tapes in melt, while the setup can also be used to measure other types of material and other configurations (i.e. tool-ply friction). The improved accessibility of the pressure platens eases specimen mounting with a

Fig. 9: Ply-ply friction curves of shear stress versus displacement for C/PEEK measured with the new friction tester at different sliding rates (a) with corresponding stress relaxation curves after cessation of the sliding movement (b), where the black rectangle highlights the yield stress τ_y . Tests conducted at a 385 °C temperature and under a 15 kPa normal pressure. In (a), the solid lines represent the average and the shaded band the standard deviation over three tests. Note that the y -axes of the plots differ, as indicated by the dashed arrows.

Fig. 10: Normal force readings during a ply-ply friction experiment for C/LM-PAEK employing a sliding rate of 125 mm/min around 50-60 s, as indicated by the dash-dotted gray lines in the inset. The measurement locations are illustrated in the schematic, coinciding with the dashed circle that encloses the contact area (black rectangle) as seen from above with the sliding movement towards the right, indicated by the arrow.

proper alignment, while the higher degree of automation for the movement of the pull clamp and the pressure application further improve the user-friendliness compared with the original friction tester (oFT).

The ply-ply friction results for different constant sliding rates as measured with the oFT and the nFT for C/PEEK and C/LM-PAEK will be presented in flow curves of the

peak and long-time matrix shear stress versus the applied sliding rate to ease the comparison of the data sets. First, though, full friction responses, corresponding stress relaxation curves, and normal force readings will be presented for clarity.

4.1 Ply-ply friction measurement

The full friction curves of shear stress versus displacement for C/PEEK as measured with the nFT are shown in Fig. 9a for selected sliding rates. The solid lines represent the average with the shaded band the standard deviation over three measurements. The friction response at higher sliding rates resembles the schematically illustrated one in Fig. 8, in which a peak shear stress τ_p and a long-time shear stress τ_∞ at the end of the measurement can be identified. For these sliding rates, the long-time shear stress τ_∞ was computed as the average shear stress over the final 2 mm of displacement. At lower sliding rates, the shear stress grows monotonically towards a stationary regime without exhibiting a peak, meaning that the peak and long-time shear stress coincided, and were both evaluated directly after the start-up response. We observed a similar rate-dependent friction response for the same material in our earlier work [30, 31], as measured with our original friction tester.

Fig. 9b shows the stress relaxation curves corresponding to the friction responses depicted in Fig. 9a. The curves all relax towards a residual stress or yield stress τ_y , as highlighted by the black rectangle. Such a yield stress was also observed in our earlier work [30, 31] and in other studies on friction for UD C/PEEK [12, 49], which is possibly due to fiber-fiber interactions [46–48], as mentioned before. In

Fig. 11: Flow curves of peak $\tau_{mat,p}$ (triangles) and long-time matrix shear stress $\tau_{mat,\infty}$ (circles) as a function of the applied sliding rate V for (a) C/PEEK at 385 °C and (b) C/LM-PAEK at 365 °C under a 15 kPa normal pressure, measured with the new friction tester (black) and original friction tester (blue). For C/PEEK, measurement data from our earlier work [31] are added in red.

this work, the measured yield stress was on average 2.0 kPa (nFT) and 2.1 kPa (oFT) for C/PEEK and 0.7 kPa (nFT) and 0.5 kPa (oFT) for C/LM-PAEK, from which the matrix shear stress τ_{mat} was obtained according to Eq. (2).

The measured normal forces during a friction experiment at 125 mm/min for C/LM-PAEK are shown in Fig. 10. The schematic illustration shows the locations of the compression load cells from the top, placed on a circle just outside of the contact area of the pressure platens (black rectangle) with the arrow indicating the sliding direction. The measured normal forces were very constant throughout the measurement. The inset highlights the effect of the sliding action on the normal force readings, where the vertical dash-dotted lines depict the start and end. Only minor variations in the normal forces occurred during the sliding movement.

4.2 Comparison original and new setup

Figures 11a and 11b show the flow curves of the measured peak $\tau_{mat,p}$ (triangles) and long-time matrix shear stress $\tau_{mat,\infty}$ (circles) as a function of the applied sliding rate V for C/PEEK and C/LM-PAEK, respectively. Measurements with the nFT are shown in black, while the blue symbols denote the measurements with the oFT. For C/PEEK, friction data from earlier measurements performed with the oFT as part of our previous work [31] are added by the red symbols in Fig. 11a.

The ply-ply friction results for C/PEEK measured with the nFT and oFT in this work correlate well, as shown by the coinciding symbols in Fig. 11a. The earlier measurements with the oFT, performed more than two years ago in our earlier work [31], also overlap with the current data. A plateau appears for the long-time matrix shear stress $\tau_{mat,\infty}$ at high sliding rates, which reads around 35 kPa, irrespec-

tive of the friction tester used. Hence, a similar friction for C/PEEK was obtained with the nFT compared with the oFT, which suggests that the new friction tester works as expected.

The flow curves of C/LM-PAEK measured with the nFT and oFT are shown in Fig. 11b by the black and blue symbols, respectively. Again, the general friction response as obtained with the nFT and oFT is similar. Both setups result in a peak shear stress that increases with an increase in sliding rate, while a plateau emerges for the long-time shear stress at high sliding rates. However, when looking carefully at the flow curves in Fig. 11b, the correlation between the data sets from the nFT and oFT is less strong compared with C/PEEK. The overall friction measured with the nFT is slightly lower compared with the oFT measurements. The scatter in the friction data from both setups is also larger for C/LM-PAEK compared with the friction results for C/PEEK (see Fig. 11a). Measurements from our earlier work for C/LM-PAEK are not shown for the sake of clarity, though roughly overlap with the current oFT data. The measured $\tau_{mat,\infty}$ -plateau is around 42 kPa for the nFT, while slightly larger when measured with the oFT (around 55 kPa). Noteworthy to emphasize is that the specimens used in both setups were cut from the same roll, within a few meters, ruling out batch-to-batch variations as a plausible cause for the minor difference in friction as observed for C/LM-PAEK.

All in all, the new friction tester performed well, offering more ways of testing for future work, such as the ply-ply friction response for varying sliding rates. More future work would be to benchmark the oFT and nFT against more experimental setups, preferably including several different materials, to further investigate the differences and similarities of the friction setups in a broader perspective.

5 Conclusion

We developed a new experimental setup to measure friction, in particular for thermoplastic composite (TPC) tape in melt. This new friction tester, an improved version of our original setup, combines an enhanced user-friendliness, controllability, and specimen accessibility with new test capabilities such as specimens with off-axis fiber orientations and the ability to vary the sliding rate during a test. The new setup, therefore, eases and broadens the scope of the friction characterization for TPC tapes.

The design of the new friction tester is based on our original setup combined with our advancing insights and the recommendations of a benchmark on several setups performed earlier. A setup with horizontal pressure platens was chosen to reduce the challenges related to gravity, while the pressure platens doubled in size compared with the original setup to reduce edge effects. Part of the frame is hinged such that the pressure platens can be opened, providing a good accessibility when mounting a specimen. An air bellow was used to apply the normal pressure between the pressure platens, actively controlled by means of three compression load cells placed in a triangle, which also enables checking the force distribution. A guiding system, balanced by a counterweight, controls the translational movement of the pressure platen, while allowing for rotation over the in-plane axes for a proper pressure distribution.

Ply-ply friction tests for UD C/PEEK and C/LM-PAEK in melt were performed for a wide range of constant sliding rates to compare the friction results of the new and original friction tester. A good correlation was obtained for C/PEEK, which suggests that the new friction tester works as expected. The friction response for C/LM-PAEK as measured with the new friction tester was slightly lower compared with the original setup, though the overall friction behavior was similar.

Data availability

The supplementary data for this article is available in the [4TU.ResearchData](https://doi.org/10.4121/96b79ea3-9c84-444a-a7ed-e084192f045e) data repository (DOI: 10.4121/96b79ea3-9c84-444a-a7ed-e084192f045e).

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